

1 Introduction

2 Complications resulting from pregnancy and childbirth are a leading cause of death among
3 15-19-year-old adolescent girls in low- and middle income countries (LMIC) (Sulley et al.,
4 2020). Historically, health organisations have invested heavily in finding ways to address
5 adolescent sexual and reproductive health (ASRH) needs, but typically defining problems and
6 solutions for adolescents, rather than with them. This creates significant risks for
7 misinterpretation of what the problem is and makes assumptions about the types of solutions
8 that might work best. One strategy that organisations have used to increase the effectiveness
9 of ASRH programs is active youth participation. However, there is often a lack of youth
10 engagement in designing interventions (Villa-Torres & Svanemyr, 2015).

11 Human-centred design (HCD) is an umbrella term that describes a creative design process
12 that is a flexible, yet disciplined and repeatable approach to solving complex problems. At its
13 core, HCD involves adopting a mindset prioritising the needs and experiences of the
14 population of interest (Holeman & Kane, 2020). HCD practitioners have increasingly become
15 involved in design and implementation of a myriad of projects within global health (Holeman
16 & Kane, 2020). However, there is some contention over the value of HCD in global health—
17 in particular, what the process offers in comparison to established approaches to public health
18 intervention design that are grounded in socio-behavioural research (Tolley, 2016).

19 Youth-led participatory action research (YPAR), a form of community-based participatory
20 research (CBPR), uses methods and pedagogy to focus on young people's lived experience
21 (Anyon, Bender, Kennedy, & Dechants, 2018). Fully realised, YPAR engages youth as
22 partners and collaborators in an iterative cycle of program research, design, and evaluation.
23 Due to resource and time constraints, program designers may choose to select specific
24 moments during a project to engage components of the YPAR strategy, without embracing
25 the full model. YPAR has primarily been shown to improve the health and wellbeing of youth

1 researchers, although some evidence suggests that actively involving recipients in formative
2 research leads to more effective programs (Ozer, 2016).

3 A recent review comparing HCD and community-based participatory research (CBPR)
4 approaches concluded that integrating HCD in CBPR projects may lead to more innovative
5 solutions that have greater reach, and are more readily adopted (Chen, Leos, Kowitt, &
6 Moracco, 2020). Chen et al. focused on five instrumental strategies practitioners can draw
7 from HCD when conducting CBPR projects: (1) form transdisciplinary teams, (2) centre
8 empathy, (3) recruit and work with “extreme users”— individuals purposively selected
9 because they fall at the far end of the spectrum of a given characteristic — as participants and
10 partners, (4) rapidly prototype elements of the product or service, and (5) create tangible
11 products or services that can be tested. In this article, we present a case study of an HCD
12 process enhanced by components of YPAR and reflect on the challenges and opportunities of
13 five instrumental strategies for integrated HCD into CBPR proposed by Chen et al. (2020).

14 [Adolescents 360](#)

15 Adolescents 360 (A360) is a four-and-a-half-year initiative to increase modern contraceptive
16 use among 15 to 19-year old girls in Nigeria, Ethiopia, and Tanzania. The programme is
17 implemented by a global consortium which brings together a transdisciplinary team of HCD
18 practitioners, ASRH programmers, social marketers, and researchers from varied disciplines
19 (public health, adolescent developmental science, anthropology). Although this began as an
20 adult-designed project with categorical funding focused on contraception, a primary principle
21 was meaningful youth engagement. The purpose of adopting an integrated HCD-YPAR
22 approach was to catalyse novel, scale-able, and replicable approaches to reducing unmet need
23 for contraception.

24 A360 consisted of four phases: 1) Inquiry: youth-engaged formative research to understand
25 the experiences, contexts, and underlying motivations that inform adolescent behaviour; 2)

1 Insight synthesis: collaborative analysis across expertise to generate themes to inform design;
2 3) Prototyping: quickly developing and testing rudimentary versions of solutions to
3 understand desirability, technical practicality, and generate new insights to improve solutions;
4 and 4) Adaptive implementation: ongoing inquiry and refinement, critical reflection, and
5 iterative evaluation of solutions.

6 Inquiry

7 Formative research was conducted to understand the experiences, contexts, and underlying
8 motivations that inform adolescent behaviour. Data were collected by teams comprised of
9 programme staff, HCD practitioners, and 111 youth designers (20 in Ethiopia; 16 in Nigeria
10 and 75 in Tanzania; see Table 1). A theoretically driven youth engagement process informed
11 the training and support for youth and adults engaged in the programme (Ozer, 2016). Adults
12 and youth designers attended one of three “bootcamps”: short, intensive courses on effective
13 youth-adult partnerships; HCD; and data collection, analysis, and ethical research. Approval
14 was obtained from US- and country-based ethical review boards.

15 [Insert Table 1 here]

16 Teams collected data using a range of qualitative research methods (e.g. observations,
17 promoted discussions, photo narratives, card sort and in-depth interviews). During formative
18 research, youth designers acted as note-takers, interpreters, and interviewers. Topic guides
19 comprised open-ended questions exploring respondents’ perception of their lives, goals,
20 needs, and engagement in health services. Teams also conducted market analyses and
21 audience segmentation to identify the benefits and drawbacks of varied service delivery
22 channels, and the opportunities and challenges to improve coverage and outreach to
23 adolescents through health sector models. These findings were iteratively incorporated into
24 recruitment strategies. Subsequently, teams interviewed married and unmarried, in- and out-
25 of-school, 15-to-19-year-old girls, their male partners, parents, community influencers, and

1 health providers in rural, urban, and peri-urban settings. In total, qualitative data was
2 collected from 750 participants (294 in Ethiopia; 365 in Nigeria and approximately 100 in
3 Tanzania, where data from a previous HCD project informed A360 design).

4 The youth-adult teams analysed iteratively in the field using simple tools (post-its and flip
5 charts). Team members described and reflected on interviews and observations, highlighting
6 extreme cases, and identifying emerging themes (IDEO.org, 2015). Youth designers
7 contributed perspectives and acted as cultural translators to interpret findings.

8 Insight synthesis and Prototyping

9 In the second and third phases, the transdisciplinary teams were reformulated, sometimes
10 including youth researchers, to systematically review the evidence and creatively brainstorm
11 ways to respond to emerging themes (for example, “How might we meet girls’ expressed
12 desire to become more financially independent?”). The in-country team leads, in partnership
13 with the HCD leads, used this data to focus on actionable insights that responded to the
14 original design challenge and drove the prototyping process. Four opportunity areas for
15 design were identified: 1) connecting girls to ASRH services relevant to their culture,
16 context, sense of self, and stage of life; 2) aligning ASRH with girls’ self-stated desire for
17 improved social and financial stability; 3) improving girls’ accurate understanding of
18 contraception; and 4) fostering trusted systems that support girls in accessing ASRH services.

19 Adult teams developed and tested 73 intervention prototypes (Tanzania=36; Ethiopia=25;
20 Nigeria=12). A set of design standards were used to assess the desirability, feasibility and
21 viability of intervention prototypes which enabled teams to create user-centred, context-
22 specific interventions. To consider the viability of the project at scale, adult teams then
23 refined the solutions and selected the final design based on feedback from girls, their
24 influencers (e.g. male partners, parents), and health system stakeholders (e.g. Ministry of
25 Health, medical providers).

1 Adaptive implementation

2 In the final phase, adult teams piloted the interventions and then transitioned to an evidence-
3 based adaptive implementation phase in which adults and youth collaborated for continuous
4 program improvement as interventions expanded across geographic catchment areas. Youth
5 participated as staff members and researchers during this period. Across all countries, the
6 interventions offer girls aspirational program elements (e.g. life goals planning, financial
7 skills) as part of connecting girls with youth-friendly opt-out contraceptive counselling and
8 on-demand method provision within the fullest extent of local law. (see (A360 Open Source,
9 2019) for full details). An independent process evaluation (including participatory action
10 research) generated additional evidence on successes, challenges, and adaptations, which fed
11 into ongoing learning and decision-making.

12 Implications for practice

13 As use of HCD increases in global health intervention design and implementation, there is an
14 increasing need to report on how HCD can enhance YPAR approaches to intervention design.
15 Below and in Table 2, we reflect on our experiences of using five instrumental strategies for
16 incorporating HCD into youth-engaged CBPR (Chen et al., 2020).

17 [Insert Table 2 here]

18 Form transdisciplinary teams

19 Chen et al. (2020) recommend including individuals with complementary skill sets from
20 seemingly unrelated fields in project teams. In A360, extensive communication and careful
21 planning were needed to create convergence and understanding among the transdisciplinary
22 team and with the youth designers. Youth engagement (and other staffing models), evolved
23 throughout the project to find new ways to meaningfully engage youth after the design phase,
24 but building the skills and capacity of youth designers and adult partners was costly, both
25 financially and in terms of staff time and skill.

1 Cultivate greater empathy

2 To increase the appropriateness of interventions, Chen et al. recommend centring empathy
3 early and often by collecting qualitative data from users in the context of their everyday lives.
4 Engaging youth as action researchers during adaptive implementation helped identify
5 opportunities to improve program empathy and responsiveness to user perspectives.
6 However, we recommend that practitioners broaden the definition of “user” at the outset of
7 formative research and explicitly cultivate empathy, not just with the primary intervention
8 priority population, but with service providers and other supply-side actors. Additionally,
9 transdisciplinary teams may need to generate consensus about how to cultivate empathy
10 (Table 2).

11 Recruit and work with extreme users

12 Including “extreme users” can spark creativity in researchers and ensure that a wide range of
13 perspectives and desires are considered (Chen et al., 2020). In the context of LMICs,
14 recruiting extreme users as project partners is frequently challenging due to security,
15 logistical concerns, and the political context. In A360, youth designers needed relatively high
16 competencies to engage with HCD practitioners effectively. Therefore, it was not feasible for
17 our YPAR to include extreme user groups as partners. Youth designers tended to be more
18 urban, have higher educational attainment and be from higher socio-economic groups
19 compared to the research participants. Nonetheless, youth designers helped the teams identify
20 and access extreme users as respondents (Table 2).

21 Rapidly prototype

22 Prototyping ideas that emerge from design research insights could increase efficacy and
23 adoption (Chen et al., 2020). In A360, resource constraints led to less youth involvement
24 during the prototyping process than the research stage. In Tanzania, we obtained additional
25 funding to recruit a team of youth experts to work alongside implementers to develop and roll
26 out innovations to improve girls’ engagement. Based on this positive experience, we

1 recommend that practitioners ensure sufficient resources to sustain youth engagement. Some
2 prototypes challenged existing bodies of evidence from one specific discipline, but were
3 promoted by insights generated through design research. We resolved tensions over such
4 conflicting evidence claims by returning to best practices: testing and then refining sub-
5 components of prototypes rather than creating interventions unsupported by evidence.

6 Create tangible products or services

7 Chen et al. (2020) recommend creating and testing tangible solutions (e.g., products,
8 services) in real-time. We found this to be useful during prototyping; however, our
9 experience (Table 2) demonstrated the importance of clarifying the purpose of tangible
10 products or services. While tangible products are valuable because they make prototypes or
11 concepts “real”, and allow practitioners to assess stakeholder reactions, these tangible
12 elements often evolve as they come together, in part or whole, to form the final intervention
13 model and strategy. The tangible solutions are not the “core” of the intervention, and fidelity
14 to original designs should not be the primary goal. What is essential is the user journey—the
15 intended adolescent experience of the intervention—and the design principles that inform
16 tangible components and the theory of change upon which the designed solution is based. In
17 A360, understanding implementation in terms of fidelity to this user journey has been
18 paramount, and has required the involvement of young people. Youth should have myriad
19 roles in this pursuit—as research respondents, researchers, and staff empowered to adapt in
20 response to emerging adolescent client experience.

21 Conclusion

22 Chen et al offer a useful framework for reflection on how HCD can enhance YPAR for
23 intervention design and implementation. For A360, a key proposed area for continued
24 learning is meaningful partnership with ‘extreme’ adolescent users throughout design and
25 implementation.

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1 *Table 1: Attributes of youth as part of Adolescents 360 design teams*

Profile	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Young women and men aged 18-25 years who had completed at least the first stage of secondary education. • Demonstrated strong verbal and written communication skills, fluency in local languages and an adequate level of conversational English
Roles & Activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participation in training of teams on power-sharing, effective youth-adult partnerships, and meaningful youth engagement shifted the project from a passive model of youth as sources of data and intervention recipients, towards a model of youth working with adults as partners, advocates, designers, and analysts. • Youth designers fully participated in the inquiry phase and were re-engaged during critical moments of subsequent phases as deemed appropriate and feasible by each in-country team. • During the inquiry phase, youth and adults worked as partners in a systematic and cyclical process of reviewing existing evidence; collecting and analysing data; and identifying design opportunities. • In later design phases, youth engaged in other activities including advocating for social and policy change; designing and testing prototypes; and vetting and refining intervention approaches.
Contributions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Current, lived youth experience • Understanding of social and cultural influences on adolescence and young adulthood specific to each country of implementation • Expertise in local languages and dialects as they partnered with adult colleagues to research and design country-specific interventions.
Example	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Formative research in Ethiopia indicated that financial planning could be used as an entry point to discuss contraception with newly married couples. The team focused efforts on constructing a dialogue process that Health Extension Workers (HEWs) could implement. The conversation brings young married girls and couples on a cognitive journey from life goal setting, to financial planning, to understanding the value of contraceptives as a tool to support progress towards their goals around securing a healthy and stable future for their family. In this process HEWs support young married money (the Ethiopian birr). Through iteratively inquiring and prototyping with local youth in participating regions, youth designers identified sacks of teff--a staple food crop used to make a fermented flatbread-- as a relatable unit of cost. Teams then developed and prototyped a series of job aids and discussion and training guides to enable HEWs to conduct contraceptive counselling in a way that was relevant to the life and financial literacy of the participants.

2

Table 2: Adolescents 360 experiences of integrating human centred design strategies within participatory research projects. Adapted from Chen et al. 2020

Recommended Action	Descriptions	Relevant case-based experiences: A360
Form transdisciplinary teams	Include individuals with complementary skill sets from “unexpected” (seemingly unrelated) fields.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Regular meetings, discussions, webinars, training, and careful work planning were needed to facilitate transdisciplinary dialogue of a physically distanced global team, agree on terms and concepts, and create convergence between the disciplines. For example, dialogue between HCD practitioners and public health researchers early in the project helped to build consensus about what constitutes “data”, “data management”, and how to reach analysis goals. Collectively the team agreed on feasible methods, aligned with research standards of the traditional researchers, that served the project’s design goals. Coming to this consensus required significant trust, vulnerability, and willingness to adapt in service of the best outcomes for the project. • Different phases of the program required different staffing models; teams evolved to incorporate staff with programmatic and clinical expertise during the prototyping phases. A360 facilitated involvement from Ministry of Health representatives from the outset of the design process, and we noted increased engagement and approval of the designed interventions compared with stakeholders who were not involved from the beginning of the project. The latter group found the HCD process confusing to follow and questioned the efficiency and utility of design research. • Embedding youth designers enhanced the validity of the analysis and interpretation of data; however, resources were limited for youth engagement, and consequently, in-country teams found it challenging to recruit and retain a sustained cohort of young people.
Cultivate greater empathy	Collect qualitative data from users in the context of their everyday lives, not just the problem to be investigated. Value all that they share.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In A360, service providers are fundamental to the delivery of the solutions, but this group was not fully considered in the initial design phase. By centring the perspectives and desires of adolescent girls, we neglected explicit cultivation of empathy with healthcare workers (e.g. deeper consideration for their workloads and flow and time constraints). While this was resolved in later stages, earlier engagement with service providers could have saved time and resources. • A360’s transdisciplinary team agreed that empathy was a central component to understanding adolescent contraceptive uptake but differed in their operational approach. For example, in HCD empathy involves “stepping into the shoes” of the end-user to see design opportunities more clearly, whereas, in anthropology, empathy is a strategy for reserving judgement or subjectivity to create space to understand cultural context deeply. The shared value of cultivating empathy reinforced the concept as a core focus throughout design activities, elevating its importance in data collection and decision-making.

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To cultivate greater empathy with adolescent girls, we used visual tools alongside interview guides that covered a broad spectrum of topics and these tools generated large quantities of data. The design research coding process occurs collaboratively, relying on in-person deliberations rather than using written transcripts and documented coding. Consequently, teams (particularly those who were new to design) struggled to synthesise insights using the rapid and iterative methods usual to design research. • Compared to socio-behavioural qualitative methods, design research analysis centred on fostering empathy can lack transparency; posing difficulty in documenting how themes and insights were generated from the data.
Recruit and work with extreme users	Gather data from users who fall on the far end of the spectrum on a given characteristic. List the demographic attributes, beliefs, and behavioural attributes for typical (“mainstream”) and atypical (“extreme”) users and recruit these extreme users in your research, especially for intervention development.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In the context of LMICs, recruiting and working with extreme users was frequently challenging due to security, logistical concerns, and the political context. For example, in Ethiopia, inflexible interview timings limited the profile of respondents, and it was difficult to recruit male partners of adolescent girls since they may have feared the legal repercussions of being identified as married to a minor. • Prioritising the safety of participants, especially when exploring sensitive topics, sometimes took precedence over including extreme users. In A360, issues affecting adolescent girls experiencing sexual and gender-based violence could not be explored in-depth without compromising the privacy and safety of this group by isolating them from “mainstream” users.
Rapidly prototype	Test different ideas quickly for immediate feedback and quickly refine, build, and iterate.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • At times prototypes challenged existing bodies of evidence. For example, design insights indicated girls’ desire for stand-alone centres to offer youth-friendly services, and near-peer mentors to support outreach and follow up, yet there is evidence of the ineffectiveness of these approaches (Norton, Chandra-Mouli, & Lane, 2017). Therefore, the teams prototyped these services in a variety of versions or with various complementary components, to create an effective ecosystem of services rather than create a solution that the evidence did not support.
Create tangible products or services	Create a tangible solution that can be actually implemented and tested at the end of the research project (it can even be a piece of a product or service).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Initially, six months were allocated testing tangible solutions. However, delays during the design research phases shortened this phase to just six weeks per county. This duration was inadequate to rigorously test the solutions in real-world settings and feed data and learning back into the solutions to course correct. • Due to time and capacity constraints, teams found it challenging to balance refining tangible solutions with meeting targets and deadlines. Initially, HCD practitioners created detailed guidance manuals with instructions on how to implement the interventions with fidelity to the original design. These manuals were static examples of the interventions and, as a result,

		<p>implementation teams struggled to apply them as they continued cultivating empathy with users to improve implementation or adapt the interventions. To rectify this problem, the project co-created (with service providers and implementation teams) adaptation guidelines for each intervention. Using insights from the design research, teams distinguished between core intervention sub-components (that should not be altered) and sub-components requiring proactive iterative refinement. Adopting this segmented approach enabled teams to manage testing tangible solutions in varying real-world settings effectively.</p>
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